

Assessing the Financial Viability of 60MW Bua Hydropower Project in Malawi

Author: Isaac Chitedze

Affiliation: Power Market Limited

1. Context

- Electricity access in Malawi is just at 18%, with grid electricity contributing 11.4% while off grid solar photovoltaics accounting for the remaining 6.6%.
- The challenge is under-generation & delayed generation capacity expansion as Malawi's projected demand in 2023 is 941MW but the current installed capacity is 566.6MW.
- As of 2022, Malawi had a population of 20 million, GDP of \$11.85 per capita and urbanization rate of 16% which is projected to reach 21% by 2030

2. Aim

- Assessing the financial viability of 60MW Bua hydropower project to supply power to the grid and the end-user electricity tariff.

Figure 1: Hydropower potential sites in Malawi

3. Methods & Scenarios

- Analysis was carried out using the Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN). The project case data, plant data and financial/economic data has been collected from the developer and banks.
- The plant parameters are as follows:
 - Plant size: 60 MW installed capacity
 - Star year: 2023
 - Construction period: 3 years
 - First year operation: 2026
 - PPA term: 25 years (operation period)
 - Yearly production: 300 GWh
 - Discount rate: 10%
 - Inflation rate: 13%
 - Project finance structure: 70% debt and 30% equity

4. Results

Figure 2: Best case scenario

Figure 3: Worst case scenario

Scenario	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Normal	Non-cost-reflective tariff	-Subsidies or rebate -Constant electricity price
Worst	Construction delay	-Few financing options (more expensive) -Increase the cost of investment (equipment etc.- 20% increase) -High inflation rate (10% higher)
Best	Cost-reflective tariff (Automatic Tariff adjustment Formula [ATAF])	-Stable exchange rate -Steady inflation rate -No force majeure

Table 1: Project finance structure

5. Policy insights, conclusions and future work

Conclusions:

- The Bua 60MW hydropower project is financially viable and would contribute significantly to the energy policy goal of increasing the renewable generation capacity in the country and achieving universal energy access.
- The best-case scenario tariff in the first year of operation is \$0.045 per kWh

Policy insights:

- Under-generation challenge can be address by attracting more Independent Power Producers (private sector investment) through competitive bidding to drive down the PPA tariffs.
- To instill confidence in Independent Power Producers, the country must implement cost-reflective tariff.

6. References

- [1] Malawi Government, (2018). National Energy Policy. Available at <https://www.energy.gov.mw/1008-2/#tab-id-2-active>
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- [3] Malawi Government, (2017). Independent Power Producer (IPP) Framework for Malawi.